

Comparison of age estimation methods among 7–16-year-old patients attending a dental college in Bangalore, India

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Received: Feb 15, 2026

Accepted: Mar 13, 2026

Published: Mar 16, 2026

Abstract:

Age estimation in children and adolescents is a fundamental question and is an essential to answer a variety of legal questions. The teeth are useful predictors of age in this age-group, particularly because of their relative accuracy. There is an existence of different patterns of maturation among different populations. Aims: To evaluate the validity of Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula, Willem's method, Cameriere's method. A cross – sectional study was done in total of 100 Pre – treatment OPG's (orthopantomogram) of 7 – 16 year old patients were assessed for tooth development by using Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula, Willem's method, Cameriere's method. Mann – Whitney test is used to obtain most valid method. The Willem's method was found to be the most accurate method, followed by Cameriere's method, and Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula. Dental findings assessed by radiography are an important source of information in forensic odontological age determination.

Descriptors: Forensic odontology, Willem's method, Dental age estimation, Cameriere's method, Indian specific formula.

Key Messages: This study demonstrates that Willem's method is more valid method among Indian population and also emphasizes on the need to validate different age estimation methods for a particular population.

Key words: Dental Age Estimation, Orthopantomography, Demirjian Method, Willems Method, Cameriere Method

Introduction:

Age estimation in children and adolescents is a fundamental question and an essential answer to a variety of legal questions, including issues of status of majority and criminal liability and also in scenario's where individuals may not have accurate information about their date of birth, or they may choose to suppress such information.^{1,2,3} The teeth are useful predictors of age in this age-group, particularly because of their relative accuracy and also because of the lack of other reliable predictors.³ The method for dental age estimation using developmental stages of teeth is useful since tooth development is less influenced by environmental factors.⁴ To improve the methods for estimation of chronological age in children, various odontological methods have been developed.

The most common method for age estimation was Demirjian's method.⁵ However, its application on numerous populations has resulted in wide variations in age estimates and consequent suggestions for the method's adaptation to the local sample.⁶⁻⁸ Acharya A B³ carried out to check the accuracy of Demirjian's method in Indian population, since the Demirjian's method resulted in inferior age prediction Indian specific formula was developed. Willem's et al⁴ et al evaluated the accuracy of Demirjian's method in Belgian Caucasian population but scoring system was modified as a significant overestimation was reported. The adapted method was validated and resulted in more accurate dental age estimations in this population. A completely different approach was taken Cameriere et al⁹ in Italian children and a new mathematical formula was published for calculating dental age on teeth for some European countries. This is based upon measuring the completeness of apical development via a computer method.

There is a reported existence of different patterns of maturation among different populations in dental literature. Variability may mostly relate to ethnic differences, but other factors, such as gender, age climate, nutrition level, and socio – economic level may also play a role.^{10,11}

Hence, the present study aims to evaluate the validity of Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula³, Willem's method⁴ and Cameriere's⁹ dental age estimation method among young and adolescent patients attending a dental college in Bangalore, India.

Objectives of the study:

1. To measure the accuracy of each of the age estimation methods.
2. To compare and derive the best among the 3 methods.

Methodology

A cross – sectional study was conducted with the aim to evaluate the validity of the three different dental age estimation methods among young and adolescent patients attending a dental college in Bangalore. The study proposal was approved by institutional review board (protocol number - 101/2013) of Vydehi Institute of Dental Sciences and Research Centre, Bangalore. The study was conducted according to the guidelines laid down in the declaration of Helsinki and all procedures involving human subjects/patients were approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Department of Orthodontics and Pedodontics and preventive dentistry, Vydehi Institute of Dental Sciences and Research Centre, Bangalore, India. Pre – treatment OPG's (orthopantomogram) from the archives of Department of Orthodontics and Department of Pedodontics and preventive dentistry were included in the study.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Patients of age group 7 – 16 years, OPG's free from distortion
2. Radiographs of patients with full complement of teeth.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Radiographs of patients with developmental anomalies which affect the development of teeth – like facial hemihypertrophy, facial hemiatropy, agnathia, supernumerary teeth, hypodontia, distortion and crowding of teeth where the root structures of the teeth were not clearly discernible.
2. Radiographs of patients with bilaterally missing teeth.

A pilot study was conducted among 10 patients to determine the sample size and to check the intra observer reliability of the study the OPG's were analysed after a period of 2 weeks. Mann Whitney test was performed to compare the original and reassessed OPG's. A study sample of 92 was estimated with α – error considered at 5% and β – error considered at 20% and the sample size was rounded to 100.

The intra – observer reliability for Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula, Willem's method and Cameriere's method was 0.910, 0.970 and 0.705 respectively. All the OPGs meeting the inclusion criteria were scanned using dental x – ray scanner Epson V 700 (Seiko Epson Corp, Shinjuku, Tokyo, Japan) into JPEG format. The digitalized OPGs were then analyzed with

computer aided software Adobe Photoshop 7.0 (Adobe Systems Incorporated, San Jose, United States). Chronological age of the patient was masked and labelled for the study by a different examiner who is not involved in the study. A single examiner conducted the analysis of all the three methods. Dental age estimation of the patients was calculated by using Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula³, Willem's method⁴, Cameriere's method⁹.

Statistical analysis: Data were submitted to descriptive analyses and Mann Whitney test is used to obtain most accurate method. Microsoft excel and word (MS office 2010 Microsoft Corp., Redmond, WA, USA) were used to generate graphs and tables. The Statistical software SPSS 21.0 for windows (IBM Corp, Armonk, NY, USA) was used for the analysis of the data. A p – value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Wherever there is no statistically significant difference, it is concluded that the estimated mean age is almost nearer to the actual mean age and that particular method is more reliable method.

Results:

The present study was conducted to evaluate the validity of the three different dental age estimation methods among young and adolescent patients attending a dental college in Bangalore, India.

If the p -value from two or more pairs of comparison turn out to be >0.05 , the method which yields a near estimate of the actual age would be the one which has a higher p -value.

In a total of 100 study samples 45% of study sample i.e., 45 OPG's were of males and 55% of the study sample i.e., 55 OPG's were of females.

Mean chronological age was 10.95 ± 2.49 years. Estimated mean dental age for Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula, Willem's method and Cameriere's method was 12.48 ± 2.46 years, 10.87 ± 2.63 years and 10.26 ± 2.28 years respectively. (Figure – 1)

The Willem's method was found to be the most accurate method, followed by Cameriere's method, and Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula. The Willem's method was found to under estimate the age with mean difference of 0.077 years. The difference was not statistically significant (p – value 0.739). Cameriere's method was found to under estimate the age with a mean difference of 0.684 years. The difference was statistically significant (p – value 0.042). Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula was found to overestimate the age

with mean difference of 1.536 years. The difference was statistically significant (p – value <0.001). (Table – 1)

Table – 1 Comparison between chronological age with the three different age estimation methods

Method	Mean \pm S.D	S.E of Mean	Mean difference	95% CI for Mean difference		p – value
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Chronological age	10.95 \pm 2.49	0.25				
Demirjina's method using Indian specific formula	12.48 \pm 2.46	0.25	-1.536	-2.226	-0.845	$<0.001^*$
Willem's method	10.87 \pm 2.63	0.26	0.077	-0.637	0.792	0.739
Cameriere's method	10.26 \pm 2.28	0.23	0.684	0.018	1.351	0.042*

*Denotes significant difference at - $p<0.05$.

The mean chronological age for males was 10.80 \pm 2.47 years, estimated mean dental age for Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula was 12.52 \pm 2.19 years, Willem's method was 10.66 \pm 2.41 and Cameriere's method was 10.09 \pm 2.01. The mean chronological age for females was 11.06 \pm 2.53 years, estimated mean dental age for Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula was 12.45 \pm 2.68 years, Willem's method was 11.04 \pm 2.80 and Cameriere's method was 10.40 \pm 2.49 (Table – 2).

Willem's method was found to underestimate age with mean difference of 0.138 years in males and 0.028 years in females. Accuracy using Willem's method was better for females. Cameriere's method was found to under estimate the age with a mean difference of 0.706 years in males and 0.667 years in females. Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula was found to overestimate the age with mean difference of 1.723 years in males and 1.382 years in females (Table – 2).

Table – 2 Gender wise comparison between chronological age with the three different age estimation methods

Method	Gender	Mean± S.D	S.E of Mean	Mean difference	95% CI for Mean diff		p – value
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Chronological age	Males	10.80±2.47	0.37				
	Females	11.06±2.53	0.34				
Demirjina's method using Indian specific formula	Males	12.52±2.19	0.33	-1.723	-2.701	-0.745	0.008*
	Females	12.45±2.68	0.36	-1.382	-2.365	-0.399	0.016*
Willem's method	Males	10.66±2.41	0.36	0.138	-0.887	1.162	0.695
	Females	11.04±2.80	0.38	0.028	-0.980	1.036	0.945
Cameriere's method	Males	10.09±2.01	0.30	0.706	-0.238	1.650	0.134
	Females	10.40±2.49	0.34	0.667	-0.282	1.615	0.163

*Denotes significant difference at - $p < 0.05$.

Discussion:

Age estimation plays an important role in forensic medicine, paediatric endocrinology, archaeology and clinical dentistry. In forensic contexts, with respect to the dead and the relative requirement for biological profiles, assigning an age to a living child of unknown identity may be necessary.¹²

In the present study, a study sample of 100 OPGs were examined in order to ascertain the validity of Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula, Willem's method, and Cameriere's method among young and adolescent patients attending a dental college in Bangalore.

Acharya's study³, which arrived at the Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula used in the present assessment, has deduced a mean difference of 1.43 years. The mean difference in the present study was 1.536 years for the overall sample which is slightly more than the original

study. The study resulted in better age prediction in females than in males. This is comparable with Acharya's study³ and study done by Jayanth kumar.¹³

Willem's method⁴ resulted in a smaller overestimation for boys with Mean difference of 0.0 years and S.D: 0.9 years and girls with Mean difference of 0.2 years and SD: 1.3 years and was found to be more accurate in Belgian Caucasian population. In the present study Willem's method was found to underestimate age with mean difference of 0.138 years and S.D of 2.41 years in males and mean difference of 0.028 years and S.D of 2.8 years in females. Sang – Seob Lee et al¹⁴ checked the validity of Demirjian's method and Willem's method in Korean population. Dental age estimation calculated by Willem's method showed a mean underestimation of 1.54 years in males and 0.19 in females respectively. Accuracy of Willem's method was better for girls compared to boys which were in accordance with the present study. Maber et al¹⁵ checked the accuracy of age estimation of radiographic methods using developing teeth. Dental age estimation calculated by Willem's method showed a mean under estimation of 0.05 years for boys and 0.20 years for girls, which is in accordance with the present study but the accuracy was better for boys. In a study done by Cameriere et al¹⁶ among white Italian, Spain and Croatian children Willem's method showed to overestimate dental age in boys and underestimate dental age in girls. In contradiction to the present study, in various other studies done by Nik Norian Nik – Hussein,¹⁷ Balwant Rai,¹⁰ Amal A. El – Bakary et al¹⁸ Willem's method have shown an over estimation of age.

Cameriere's method⁹ which is based upon measuring the completeness of apical development via computer method has shown to under estimate the age with a mean difference of 0.706 years in males and 0.667 years in females. Similar results were found in a study done by Amal A. El - Bakary et al¹⁸ Cameriere's method resulted in a mean under estimation of age by 0.26 years for girls and 0.49 years for boys. Where as in a study done by Ivan Galic et al¹⁹ cameriere's method has shown to overestimate age with a mean difference of 0.10 years for girls and under estimate age with a mean difference of 0.02 years in males. Dental age estimation was in accordance with the present study only in boys. In contrast to the present study, study done by Balwant Rai¹⁰, has shown to overestimate dental age in both boys and girls.

Comparing the accuracy of three methods, Willem's method was more accurate than Cameriere's method, Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula. This confirms previous studies which showed Willem's method was more accurate than Cameriere's method.^{18,20,21}

However, it is contradictory to that of other studies which found that Cameriere's method was more accurate than Willem's method.^{19,22} As reported in previous studies^{3,13} incorporation of the third molars in Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula might have resulted in slightly greater errors in age estimates. Both Willem's method and Cameriere's method cannot be applied if the apices of mandibular seven teeth are closed. In such conditions Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula can be used since it includes third molar.

It is important to remember that the difference in chronological age and obtained dental ages (whatever the method used), can be attributed to numerous factors, such as the accuracy of the method's execution, the examiner's subjectivity, sample size, sample structure (age, sex, ethnicity, nationality and social status) and statistic approach to the obtained results.¹⁸

Conclusion:

In the present study Willem's method was more accurate than Cameriere's method, Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula. Both Willem's method and Cameriere's method have under estimated age in both the genders, whereas Demirjian's method using Indian specific formula has over estimated age. This shows that Willem's method is more applicable to Indian population. All the three methods are more accurate in females when compared to males.

Dentist has an important role in the recognition of abuse among persons of all ages by keeping accurate dental records and providing all necessary information so that legal authorities may recognize unknown humans.

Age estimation with OPGs can be used to make a significant percentage of forecasts in areas such as forensic medicine and forensic dentistry, especially in young patients. Radiology has become an essential tool and plays an indispensable role in the processes of human age identification. Dental radiography, a non-destructive and simple technique used daily in dental practice, has been employed in methods of age estimation, which is one of the essential tools in identification in forensic science. Dental findings assessed by radiography are an important source of information in forensic odontological age determination. Future researchers should aim at studying the ability of the model to describe the chronological age of people with different geographic locations on a larger sample size. Multifaceted interactions between different branches of dentistry with diverse disciplines like Forensic and Physical Anthropology, Odontology will merit detailed delineation.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Prof. Dr. Sandesh Pai, Head of the Department of Orthodontics and Prof. Dr. Pavan Tambakad, Head of the Department of pedodontics and preventive dentistry, Vydehi Institute of dental sciences and research centre for providing access to the archives of pre-treatment radiographs.

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